

Reduction and simplification of burdens in European agriculture through land and business registers: A value proposition

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Abstract

L'article est consacré à l'importance du registre foncier et du registre des métiers en Espagne pour l'agriculture, notamment au regard de l'Agenda 2030 ainsi que du Green Deal européen et du plan national «Recovery, Transformation and Resilience» sur la transition numérique.

Der Beitrag widmet sich der Bedeutung des Grundbuchs und Gewerberegisters in Spanien für die Landwirtschaft, insbesondere in Hinblick auf die Agenda 2030 sowie den Europäischen Green Deal und den nationalen Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan zum digitalen Wandel.

1. Land Register

In the different legal registers there are numerous matters registered, annotated or recorded by marginal note relating to institutions and legal figures closely related to agricultural law and which should be used for the purpose of streamlining the agri-food market and the rural sector in general.

Thus, the Land Register contains a great deal of information on the existence of Priority Agricultural Holdings (or family holdings, depending on the time they were set up) in relation to the farms linked to them, mainly because of the real tax implications of the subsidies granted to them and because registration also provides them with legal security in multiple relations (for example, in terms of the exercise of the special right of withdrawal¹, control of the legality of the requirements of the contributors/partners for their constitution, etc.). Without prejudice to a more exhaustive list, this Register will also include the mortgages that have been constituted on the same properties to obtain financing, the type of cultivation carried out on the property, the existence of installations on the property and their legal configuration - solar panels by means of a surface right in favour of the installer in some cases - as well as the possibility of completing the description of the property in the Register, as well as the possibility of completing the literary description of the property by georeferencing it, including not only the property but also the possibility of georeferencing constructions or even plantations (mainly trees) by specifying their coordinates in the space within the property itself.²

However, it is not only the properties in the Land Register that belong to this type of structure, but also in those cases in which movable guarantees have been constituted on assets related to the farm, such as agricultural machinery, equipment and production goods, pledges on specific fruits or harvests,

¹ Article 27 of Law 19/1995 of 4 July 1995 on the Modernisation of Agricultural Holdings.

² Article 202 of the Mortgage Law, following the reform introduced by Law 13/2015.

movable guarantees on PAC rights, etc., which also appear in the Register of Movable Goods, which frequently happens when the guarantee covers the entire production unit.

Likewise, in those cases in which a corporate form is chosen through which the agricultural or livestock farming activity is carried out, it will logically take the form of a specific type of company, either a limited liability company, public limited company, agricultural processing company, With regard to civil companies, it should be noted that the legislator, aware of the need for legal protection and information in the Commercial Register, has made it possible to register civil companies in the Commercial Register by means of the recent law on the creation and growth of companies. This register will contain their name, registered office, directors and data relevant to their actions in commerce (bankruptcy status, limitations on directors, appointments and electronic powers of attorney, closure of the company's registered office or other applicable sanctions, etc.), as well as information relating to their filing of accounts, in terms of their accounting information, their actual ownership, together with the environmental information included in their non-financial information.

The relevance of the Land, Mercantile and Movable Property Register for the provision of structured statistical data as well as homogeneous taxonomies in a country with an idiosyncrasy of autonomous regions such as Spain, has been seen on numerous occasions as a window of opportunity by the legislator when it comes to standardising certain requirements for access to the register, which is the exclusive competence of the State by application of Article 149.1.8 of the Spanish Constitution; a competence endorsed in multiple rulings by the Constitutional Court in different matters such as urban planning, housing and tourism.

A recent example in this area can be found in the *Law on waste and contaminated land for a circular economy*, approved this year, which takes up the work that was already being done in this area through the Land Registries in terms of recording the declaration of having carried out a potentially polluting activity outside the property on the occasion of its transfer, as well as the record of the declaration by an Administration of contaminated land and also the decontamination activities that can be carried out on a property.

The law establishes this obligation for any transfer and in any document, specifically for new works under any title, in the interests of speed and processing of new works, in accordance with the digitalisation of processes, the elimination of obstacles and the technical guarantees of the operators involved (architects and technical engineers) and coordination with the Cadastre.

This regulation is completed with the communications ordered by the Law to the Registrars for the preparation of the National Inventory of Contaminated Soil, in which, in addition to the marginal notes, the certifications issued and the declarations made must be communicated, together with the temporality of the same, by sending a structured file of this information on an annual basis.

In the same way, the legislator, following the path initiated by the Regulation on Public Hydraulic Domain³, now requires in this new Waste Law the need for a record of the marginal note of a land

³ Thus, Articles 9 ter, 9 quáter and 14 bis of the RDPH state that "Prior to the start of the works, the developer must have a certificate from the Land Registry stating that the construction is located in a preferential flow zone or flood zone". And in the same sense, Article 98.4 in fine of the aforementioned Draft Law on Waste and Con-

declared as contaminated by an Administration, which must be required prior to the commencement of work by any developer. This results in transparency in the real estate traffic, giving the private individual the effective possibility of being aware of this situation, which previously weighed as a hidden burden if it was not recorded.

Continuing with the legal publicity of these situations in the Land Registry, the Law⁴ also establishes the obligation to notify the competent Administration of the situation of the express and official declaration of contaminated land, determining that the way to cancel this marginal note is expressly the declaration of decontaminated land by the same Administration, to which the individual will have to accredit the activities carried out for said decontamination together with the corresponding reports. This publicity is a legal publicity and not a mere de facto publicity, being a consequence of express acts of the competent Administration for both its creation and its extinction.

We can end our reflection on the new law by also praising the technical precision of the legislator in determining the collaboration between the Ministry of Transition and the Association of Registrars, to provide the Registrars' Geoportal with the information of the State Inventory so that it can be included as associated information, both in the Registrars' Geoportal and in the registry publicity and in the notes of qualification and dispatch of documents. Currently the Registrars' Geoportal⁵ created by the Law in 2015 and recognised in numerous subsequent regulations contains a catalogue of more than two hundred WMS (web maps service) corresponding to administrative, environmental and town planning limitations that any individual can use to analyse a geometry in the territory, either by selecting a combination of all those that affect them or just one of them; and also recently used as a legal aid tool for the management of natural disasters, the La Palma volcano, large fires and floods. Making this type of information available enriches the catalogue of associated information and brings individuals and administrations closer to a better knowledge of the land environment.

It is noteworthy how the legislator on this occasion has taken up the work carried out by the Registrars to strengthen legal security in this area, using a national resource such as the Land Registry to guarantee compliance with the Law, encourage homogeneous information and standardised taxonomic indicators, linking the Land Registry, the Administration and individuals, strengthening legal security and increasing the guarantees for security in the property market, avoiding hidden charges and determining the value of land through effective knowledge of it and taking a further step to avoid *greenwashing*. It has not had to resort to new inventions, nor to ad hoc administrative registers, it has not wasted public funds, nor the human, spatial and technical resources of the administration to carry out a task that was already being carried out successfully and which is reinforced in the new Law,

taminated Soil for a Circular Economy establishes that: "any action in an area located on land declared or delimited as contaminated land by the corresponding autonomous community shall require that, prior to the start of the works, the developer must have a certificate from the Land Registry accrediting that there is a registry entry indicating that the construction is located on land declared contaminated".

⁴ Article 99.5 of the Draft: "The declaration of contaminated land shall be the subject of a marginal note in the Land Registry, at the initiative of the respective Autonomous Community in the terms determined by regulation by the Government. This marginal note will be cancelled when the corresponding Autonomous Community declares that the land is no longer considered as such, after verifying that the decontamination and recovery operations have been properly carried out".

⁵ <https://geoportal.registradores.org/>

facilitating access for all persons, all documents and multiple situations in relation to potentially polluting activities.

An example of good practice and of combining a traditional institution with technological advances to put them at the service of society that we bring here today as an example of our exercise is land consolidation, an institution that was already regulated by the Agrarian Reform and Development Act of 12 January 1973 on Agrarian Reform and Development and which today continues to be an essential instrument for the reorganisation of excessively fragmented property, fixing wealth in the rural area.

Law 13/2015⁶ established the obligation to register the graphic base of the properties in the Land Registry for a multitude of operations, among them it regulates in article 204, together with other administrative procedures, the access of the administrative acts of land consolidation to the Land Registry. Following the path established by the INSPIRE Directive⁷ in relation to geopositioning as an instrument of detailed information to be developed and cultivated, as well as the possibility of completing the description of the properties with the registration of the graphic base relating to the same. Thus, we have a literary description that is complemented and perfected by the graphic description of the same. In other words, the land register has "eyes" and "vision of the physical reality", regulating the coordination of the legal reality in the land register in an exact manner, thus strengthening the description of the object by attributing the effects of article 38 of the Mortgage Law to the co-ordinate properties, i.e. the property exists, in the form determined in the respective entry, under the protection of the courts.

For the registration of the aforementioned graphic bases, Law 13/2015 creates an auxiliary graphic qualification tool for the Registrar that has been developed by CORPME and validated by ISDEFE, under the principles of integrity, security and technological neutrality.

Thus, the aforementioned project, with the collaboration of the Administration, with the collaboration of the Registrars involved, of the technical teams of the Association and as a result of coordinated action and absolute collaboration, has led to the unblocking and registration in the last year of 1.301 properties in Aragón, 1,179 properties in Navarra, 22,426 properties in Castilla y León, 22,674 properties in Galicia, a total of 47,580 properties, 47,580 owners who have obtained their title deeds, 47,580 properties that have been placed on the market. If we take the average price of dry farming (as it is the lowest)⁸ : 7,100 €, multiplied by 47,580 farms, we have a minimum result of 337,818,000 euros injected directly into the market, without taking into account the profitability of these farms.

This valuation makes it possible for citizens to have access to flexible credit. The 1944 Mortgage Law's own Explanatory Memorandum established among its aims the promotion of and access to territorial wealth through mortgage guarantees. In this way, making all these properties available on the mortgage market enables the development of agricultural, livestock and agri-food industry projects

⁶ Law 13/2015, of 24 June, on the Reform of the Mortgage Law approved by Decree of 8 February 1946 and of the revised text of the Law on Real Estate Cadastre, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2004, of 5 March. BOE.es - BOE-A-2015-7046 Law 13/2015, of 24 June, on the Reform of the Mortgage Law approved by Decree of 8 February 1946 and of the revised text of the Law on Real Estate Cadastre, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2004, of 5 March.

⁷ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>

⁸ https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/encuestadepreciosdelatierra2020_tcm30-576897.pdf.

through mortgage credit, encouraging the establishment of life projects linked to them, the creation of employment and the fixation of population in rural areas, which is so necessary at present.

2. Future and perspective of the subject, connection with the 2030 Agenda, as well as with the European Green Pact and the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan. The need to update agricultural processing companies.

The new horizon set by the European Union through the Green Pact and the Recovery Plan has been motivated on the one hand by a need to accelerate the digital transformation of our business fabric and the way society relates and interacts. This situation was precipitated by the Global Pandemic caused by the Coronavirus that changed the ways people interact due to the need for confinement and isolation, as well as by the current situation of the invasion of Ukraine by Russia, highlighting our energy dependence and the need to accelerate sustainable policies and the importance of the primary sector (agriculture, livestock, fisheries and forestry) and food industry, as well as the supply chain with special importance of transport and food traceability, together with unstoppable inflation.

Thus, with more than 433 million people infected worldwide and more than 6 million dead, the European Union's priorities and challenges at the Versailles Summit were: Defence (to strengthen our capabilities), energy (to limit our dependence) and the economy (to create a robust economic base).

The necessary social response is to mobilise the EU budget and the European Investment Bank to protect jobs and support SMEs through SURE (Temporary European Emergency Unemployment Risk Relief Instrument) which provides funding to Member States of up to 100 billion euros; together with liquidity measures (to help businesses, in particular SMEs up to 200 billion euros and the European Stability Mechanism 240 billion euros).

Thus, in the Economic Recovery Plan to mobilise the necessary investments and to kick-start the economy, the Commission proposes two instruments: The reinforced EU Budget of EUR 1.1 trillion and a new recovery instrument Next Generation EU endowed with EUR 750 billion with the guarantee of the EU budget.

A common European response focused on investment is therefore urgently needed, also motivated by the recapitalisation needs of companies with financing problems and a growing deficit in public and private investment caused by the fall in investment due to the crisis. It is necessary to promote in this common response and action a green and digital transition and to support strategic value chains.

The six priorities of the European Commission 2019-2024 were identified through: A European Green Pact, An economy at the service of citizens, A Europe fit for the digital age, Protecting our European way of life, A stronger Europe in the world and A new European drive for democracy.

The Spanish recovery plan is structured around ten driving policies⁹, including the following policies that have a direct impact on the agricultural, livestock, forestry and food industry sectors: Urban and rural agenda and the fight against depopulation, resilient infrastructures and ecosystems, fair and inclusive energy transition, modernisation and digitisation of the ecosystem of our companies, modernisation of the tax system for inclusive and sustainable growth.

The European Green Deal entails the Transformation of the EU economy towards a sustainable future through the following milestones: A higher level of EU climate ambition for 2030 and 2050, affordable and secure clean energy supply, mobilising industry for a clean circular economy, efficient use of energy and resources in construction and renovation, mobilising research and fostering innovation towards zero pollution in a toxics-free environment, preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity; "from farm to fork": a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system as well as accelerating the transition to sustainable and smart mobility. And all this through financing the transition by positioning the EU as a world leader and leaving no one behind (Just Transition) of the European Climate Pact.

The Taxonomy is to be used in this context with the aim of mobilising private capital, through public-private collaboration and in the case of Spain under the supervision of the IGAE, which, in order to ensure compliance with the requirements of the Plan, the Responsible Authority will have access to the information residing in other systems, in particular the National Subsidies Database, the Public Sector Contracting Platform and the Register of Real Estate Ownership, as well as the Companies Register, being empowered to incorporate into the system the documentation it deems appropriate in accordance with the scope of its competence.¹⁰

In this line of compliance and in order to facilitate and expedite the processing and verification of the solvency of the recipients of funds, CORPME (the Spanish Association of Registrars) has already entered into multiple agreements with entities and administrations directly involved in the analysis of corporate solvency and anti-fraud, such as the Official Credit Institute, in order to promote transparency and financial information of companies registered in the Commercial Register, and in relation to the Register of Real Ownership with entities and administrations directly involved in the analysis of corporate solvency and anti-fraud, Bank of Spain, the Treasury, the Treasury, the General Intervention of the State Administration, the National Securities Market Commission, the National Markets and Competition Commission and the State Attorney General's Office, among other leading operators in supervising and pursuing effective compliance not only with the aims pursued by the plan but also with the requirements for accessing it. Thus, failure to file accounts with the Mercantile Registry or their discrepancy with the net results of the fiscal years with the Tax Agency will determine the reduction and/or exclusion of companies from access to the aforementioned funds, guaranteeing the legal certainty and transparency required by the EU for their allocation.

⁹ https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/temas/fondos-recuperacion/Documents/160621-Plan_Recuperacion_Transformacion_Resiliencia.pdf.

¹⁰ Article 11 of Order HFP/1030/2021 of 29 September, which sets up the management system for the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan. <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/o/2021/09/29/hfp1030#:~:text=Orden%20HFP/1030/2021%2C%20de%2029%20de%20septiembre%2C%20por%20la%20que%20se%20configura%20el%20sistema%20de%20gesti%C3%B3n%20del%20Plan%20de%20Recuperaci%C3%B3n%2C%20Transformaci%C3%B3n%20y%20Resiliencia.>

Along these lines, the recent Insolvency Act also provides for a system of early warnings of states of insolvency to be detected through the Public Insolvency Register and the Commercial Register.

It should be noted that the Business Register itself is interconnected with Europe through the BRIS Platform¹¹, which is the mechanism used by legal operators in the European and international market to find out which companies are contracting in the common territory; The information contained in the Companies Register is decisive when it comes to parameterising a company as a candidate for the allocation of external public or private investment. It has already been included in the Climate Change Act¹² the obligation to publish in its management report an annual report assessing the financial impact on the company of the risks associated with climate change generated by exposure to its activity, including the risks of the transition to a sustainable economy and the measures adopted to address these risks in order to streamline their treatment and classification. Thus, the Companies Register is the obligatory access point for sustainability reporting at European level.

Furthermore, it should be borne in mind that the Administrative Registers of the Autonomous Communities of Agricultural Processing Companies, as well as the central administrative register of the same, do not send any information to the Public Insolvency Register¹³, thus configuring dispersed systems of publicity and lacking the effect of legal publicity of the latter, the Public Insolvency Register being competent for the publicity of situations of company insolvency, as we have mentioned.

Furthermore, it is worth highlighting the interconnection of the Public Insolvency Register with the insolvency resolution registers of the other Member States of the European Union, which is carried out in accordance with the European rules that regulate it. In this way, the role of these registers is recognised in the European context as an essential source of legal information to facilitate the procedures of citizens, lawyers, public administrations, companies and other interested parties. These registers enable banks, creditors, business partners and consumers to access official and reliable information on insolvency cases, ensuring transparency and legal certainty in EU and international markets. This provision is also reflected in the regulation of the first section of the register, which provides for publicity of the opening of insolvency proceedings opened in another Member State when so requested by the insolvency practitioner.

This clamour for access for absolutely all legal persons to the commercial world, with protection for its members from personal limitation of capital and risk, regulating markets and economic transactions, interconnected with Europe, coordinated with the main evaluators, supervisors and in line with fraud and money laundering prevention policies, in a world that for the sake of transparency needs to know its structures to target risks of enemies of NATO allies, compliance with supranational limitations and prohibitions on the contracting and holding of goods derived from the invasion of Ukraine, as well

¹¹ Business Registers Interconnection System.

¹² Article 32 Law 7/2021 of 20 May on climate change and energy transition. https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2021-8447.

¹³ The Public Insolvency Register depends on the Ministry of Justice, which entrusts its management to the Association of Property, Mercantile and Movable Property Registrars of Spain. It is the Commercial Courts, Solicitors, Commercial Registrars, Notaries, Insolvency Administrators, Chambers of Commerce and the public registers of persons who provide the information on the different insolvency proceedings and out-of-court settlement files to be included in the Register. Royal Decree 892/2013, of 15 November, which regulates the Public Insolvency Register. https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2021-8447.

as the inevitable mirror policies of Europe in the framework of international trade through due diligence, is being addressed and taken up by the legislator as we can see in the latest laws mentioned, thus placing Spanish producers in a more competitive position in qualitative terms.

Continuing with the possibility of improving the agri-food legal environment through legal registers, it is worth highlighting the legislator's lack of success with the creation of a Register of food contracts signed with primary producers and their groups.¹⁴ This register is created mainly to try to avoid the sales at a loss that occur in the primary sector in the sale of products such as milk, grapes, etc. The practices of large buyers and cooperatives in these contracts consisted of adding a general clause stating that the selling price was higher than the production costs. This has led to legal uncertainty in the sector, as it is difficult to prove in the contract itself. Thus, attempts are being made to make specific "calculators" of these costs by parameterising them, which is a *diabolical probatio* in the present day, as has been demonstrated with the invasion of Ukraine and the cutting of the supply chain, together with the closures of farms, as on many occasions the price of electricity, animal feed, fertilisers, herbicides, etc., have determined that the cost is greater than the benefit, producing a national paralysis. As the Comisión Nacional del Mercado de Valores has estimated in a fierce criticism in its report on this administrative register, calculating an annual cost of 17 million euros.

Nevertheless, and independently of this register, it would be desirable that the regulations make it compulsory to deposit model food contracts in the Register of General Terms and Conditions of Business in order to achieve real protection for small and medium-sized farmers and stockbreeders.

Many users who have entered into a contract containing general terms and conditions are unaware of the exact terms and conditions that will bind them, and it may be essential to know what the terms of the contract were, what they were bound to, and how they can now withdraw from the contract and, if so, what the consequences will be. In this way, the small print of the contracts will cease to be small print.

Final court judgments declaring clauses that were part of these contracts to be null and void must be submitted by the legal representatives to the Register of General Conditions for registration.

Once a final judgment has been registered, it will have preliminary effects in other proceedings concerning identical clauses.

The aim is that a single ruling on the unfairness of certain clauses can resolve thousands of complaints, so that if unfair clauses identical to those declared null and void are subsequently used, it will not be necessary to litigate again, provided that the same party is involved. This is why it is so important to publicise the content of such judgments through the Register.

The Registry provides that, in those cases in which, once the final nullity judgment has been registered, the use of clauses declared judicially null and void as a consequence of an individual or collective

¹⁴ Law 16/2021 of 14 December amending Law 12/2013 of 2 August on measures to improve the functioning of the food supply chain . https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2021-20630.

action persists, the registrar may note the persistence in the use of such clauses, notifying the Ministry of Justice of the fact.

The Spanish Association of Registrars, through the online version of the Register (www.registradores.org) with a unified database for the entire Spanish territory, disseminates a Register that is the main instrument in the Law, providing the market with transparency, security and linking all legal operators.

In Europe the protective function in systems with legal registers like ours, such as Germany and Switzerland, qualifies the entire document for which registration is sought. The superiority of the system of maximum protection of the Land Register has been highlighted in the document Guidelines of the United Nations Commission for Europe, with key criteria followed by the General Conditions Register itself, when it considers that the ideal system of Registration must meet what it calls the principles of mirror, curtain and guarantee, according to which the Register must faithfully reflect reality; it must be sufficient to consult it, without the need to make extra-registrar enquiries and the Register must guarantee the accuracy of what it publishes.

Taking up the relationship of the Land Registry now in terms of environmental protection and improving the classification of properties and estates (thus determining the classification and label of the same, constituting the basis on which mortgage portfolios are built for subsequent issues of mortgage bonds and mortgage bonds through the securitisation of the same and being the main exponent of avoiding the dreaded *greenwashing*), and contributing directly to a green transition of real estate assets, it should be noted that following the 2015 reform of the Mortgage Law, Land Registrars have taken on a fundamental task for the protection and safeguarding of the environment and biodiversity: the registration of the graphic base of the properties in the Land Registry. The access of the coordinates of the perimeter of the property in the Land Register not only produces strong legal effects to the graphic inscription, but also entails an exhaustive examination by the Registrar of the territory affected by the inscription. The computer file of the plan is introduced into the graphic system of the Registrar, which is equipped with the associated environmental information, to see what may be affected. Let us look at some examples today of the information that the Registrar checks on the territory when admitting the property or the rights over it and which have a direct impact on Sustainable Development Objectives: Thus, in relation to Protected Natural Spaces it allows the visualisation and consultation of the information of the different figures of protection (Parks, Nature Reserves, Marine Protected Areas, Natural Monuments, Protected Landscapes); Sites of Community Importance (SCI), Special Areas of Conservation (SAC), which together with the Special Protection Areas for Birds (SPA) make up the Natura 2000 Network; Biosphere Reserves, which are areas belonging to terrestrial or coastal ecosystems proposed by the different Member States and recognised at international level by the "Man and Biosphere" programme. They include a wide variety of natural environments and seek to integrate the protection of existing natural elements with the protection of traditional forms of sustainable exploitation of natural resources. The digital layer is harmonised by the Nature Data Bank with the information provided by the different competent authorities. The Ramsar Convention, or Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat, establishes at international level a network of wetlands known as the Ramsar List.

Maps of Areas of Significant Potential Flood Risk that allow the visualisation and consultation of the set of data representing the watercourses designated as Areas of Significant Potential Flood Risk, which

have become so important in recent times; The cartography of the Public Hydraulic Domain, defined in a series of studies carried out by the competent water authorities, as well as the Easement and Police Zones associated with each area. It is the area of land corresponding to the alvee or natural channel of a continuous or discontinuous stream covered by water at the maximum ordinary floods, determined according to its geomorphological and ecological characteristics and taking into account existing hydrological, hydraulic, photographic and cartographic information, as well as available historical references. The data set of the Public Maritime Terrestrial Domain includes cartographic and alphanumeric information on beaches, wetlands, vertical cliffs and determines the protection and sustainable use of the coastline. Due to the sensitivity and fragility of the coasts, their conservation and protection is preserved by the Registrar in order to guarantee their public use, regulate the rational use of the assets and achieve an adequate level of quality of the waters and the seashore. Also the Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance, which allows us to visualise and consult the set of data on protected coastal and marine areas that guarantee the survival of the biological values and resources of the Mediterranean; contain ecosystems typical of the Mediterranean area or habitats of endangered species, or that are of special scientific, aesthetic or cultural interest. They are declared under the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona, 1976) and in the same sense the Cartography related to the Water Framework Directive. This is about the specific protection of biodiversity and water by the Registrar as an example, although a more in-depth study could be carried out in other areas in which it intervenes in the same way in relation to issues such as mountains, counties and activities that may have a direct impact on people's health.

This protection of the public domain and qualification of environmental legality by the Registrar is necessary for the effective knowledge of all those people who want to start a project on any type of land. In the same way that nobody would think of proceeding with the purchase or acquisition of a property or estate without knowing the state of encumbrances (mortgages, embargoes, etc.) that may weigh on the property, we must also be aware of the administrative and environmental limitations that exist on the same in this regard.

3. Annex: Examples of marginal notes on environmental matters

- **Article 9 of the HL:**

Where this is established, the corresponding urban planning, environmental or administrative qualification shall be indicated in a note in the margin, with the date to which it refers.

- **Article 28 of Royal Legislative Decree 7/2015, of 30 October, approving the revised text of the Law on Land and Urban Rehabilitation:**

In relation to new construction work, it must be accompanied by: "(a) compliance with all the requirements imposed by the legislation regulating the building for the delivery of the building to its users and (b) the granting of the necessary administrative authorisations to guarantee that the building meets the necessary conditions for its destination for the use foreseen in the applicable urban development planning and the **energy efficiency requirements** as demanded by the regulations in force, unless

the town planning legislation subjects such actions to a system of prior notification or responsible declaration, in which case those authorisations will be replaced by the documents accrediting that the notification has been made and that the period established for the corresponding activity to commence has elapsed, without the Property Register showing the existence of any optional resolution."

In the same sense, Article 7 of the Ley de Ordenación de la Edificación, as well as paragraph 3 of Article 202 of the Ley Hipotecaria.

- **Law 7/2022 of 8 April on Waste and Contaminated Land for a Circular Economy:**

Article 98. Potentially polluting activities.

1. The Government shall adopt by regulation, update and publish a list of potentially soil-polluting activities.

2. The owners of these activities shall periodically send the corresponding Autonomous Community the reports containing the information that may serve as a basis for the declaration of contaminated land.

3. Natural or legal persons owning land are obliged, on the occasion of the transfer of any real right over the same, to declare in the title deed formalising the transfer whether or not any potentially soil-polluting activity has been carried out on the transferred land. This declaration shall be the subject of a marginal note in the Land Register. This statement on potentially polluting activities must also be made by the owner in declarations of new construction by any title. This section shall also apply to operations of contribution of plots of land and allocation of plots resulting from urban development execution actions.

- **Sixth additional provision, relating to "Burnt forest land", of Royal Legislative Decree 7/2015, of 30 October, approving the revised text of the Law on Land and Urban Rehabilitation:**

These lands will remain in the status of rural land and will be used for forestry purposes, at least during the period provided for in Article 50 of the Forestry Act, with the exceptions provided for therein. The Forestry Administration must inform the Land Registry of this circumstance, by means of a certificate (containing the cadastral data identifying the property or properties in question and accompanied by a topographical plan of the burnt forest land, to an appropriate scale), which will be recorded by means of a marginal note until the expiry of the period indicated.

- **Articles 9 ter, 9 quáter and 14 of the Public Hydraulic Domain Regulation, after its modification by Royal Decree 638/2016, of 9 December,**

They provide for the developer of certain works to prove, by means of a certificate from the Land Registry, that there is an entry in the register indicating that the construction is located in a preferential flow zone.

It can be understood that, in accordance with the provisions of Article 73 of Royal Decree 1093/1997 of 4 July, the effect of these registry entries would be that of mere publicity notice, with indefinite validity, unless otherwise provided for in the regulations applicable to the specific case. It would only inform whoever consults the Register of the environmental classification or situation of the property

at the time to which the title deed giving rise to the marginal note refers, except in cases where the applicable legislation provides for a different effect.

- **Law 33/2015, of 21 September, which amends Law 42/2007, of 13 December, on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity. article 53 of this Law:**

Incorporation of geographic information in the Land Registry: (this article, although it does not establish a marginal note, should be included in this way in the folio, as the law requires this information to be publicised).

1. The perimeter information referring to protected natural spaces, the Natura 2000 Network, public utility mountains and the public domains of livestock trails and areas included in the Spanish Inventory of Wetlands, integrated in the Spanish Inventory of Natural Heritage and Biodiversity, will always be incorporated into the geographic information system of the registered property, in accordance with the provisions of mortgage legislation.

2. For these purposes and independently of other instruments or electronic environmental information sites that may be established by the Autonomous Communities within the framework of their powers, the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and the Environment shall maintain an updated online map service with geo-referenced and metadatable graphic representation, which makes it possible to identify and delimit the protected spatial areas referred to in the previous section, as well as to import their data so that they may be checked against the land registry properties in the application of the single computerised registry system. (The procedure for communication between the respective geographic information systems shall be determined by joint ministerial order of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and the Environment and the Ministry of Justice).

3. In all registry information, as well as in the qualification or dispatch notes referring to properties which, according to the georeferencing systems of registry properties, intersect or adjoin with spatial areas subject to some type of environmental determination, in accordance with the documentation included in the previous section, this circumstance shall be stated as associated territorial information and for purely informative purposes, recommending in any case, in addition, consultation with the competent environmental authorities.

- **Royal Decree 163/2014, of 14 March, creating the registry of carbon footprint, offsetting and carbon dioxide absorption projects. Second additional provision.**

Coordination with the Land Registry.

1. Ownership or other real rights of use and enjoyment may be recorded in the Land Registry in section b) of the Register created by this Royal Decree, of those CO₂ absorption projects generated in national territory related to land use, land use change and forestry that are located on a specific property.

2. The entry in the Land Registry shall be made by means of a note in the margin on the folio open to the affected property or properties, and shall be made by virtue of a certificate issued by the carbon footprint, offset and absorption project registry. This note will expire and must be cancelled after 5 years from the date of registration of the project in the carbon footprint register. This marginal note

shall also be cancelled by means of a certificate certifying the removal of the project from the administrative register.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Decree of 8 February 1946 approving the new official wording of the Mortgage Law.
- Law 13/2015, of 24 June, on the Reform of the Mortgage Law approved by Decree of 8 February 1946 and of the revised text of the Law on Real Estate Cadastre, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2004, of 5 March.
- Law 19/1995 of 4 July 1995 on the Modernisation of Agricultural Holdings.
- Draft Law on waste and contaminated land for a circular economy (621/000042) (Cong. Diputados, Serie A, núm. 57 Núm. exp. 121/000056)
- Royal Decree 849/1986, of 11 April 1986, approving the Regulations on the Public Water Domain, which implements preliminary titles I, IV, V, VI and VII of Law 29/1985, of 2 August 1985, on Water.
- Law 7/2021 of 20 May on climate change and energy transition.
- Royal Decree 892/2013, of 15 November, which regulates the Public Insolvency Register.
- Royal Decree 1776/1981 of 3 August 1981 approving the Statute governing Agricultural Transformation Companies.
- Order of 10 June 1997 for the application of the ninth additional provision and other supplementary rules of the Commercial Register Regulations.
- Comisión General de Codificación, Sección Segunda, de Derecho Mercantil sobre la "*Ponencia para la elaboración del borrador de Anteproyecto de Ley de sociedades agrarias de transformación*". Madrid, October 2018.
- Council Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/336 of 28 February 2022 implementing Regulation (EU) No 269/2014 concerning restrictive measures in respect of actions which undermine or threaten the territorial integrity, sovereignty and independence of Ukraine.
- European Commission. "*Recovery Plan for Europe*". https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/recovery-plan-europe_es
- Royal Decree-Law 36/2020 of 30 December, approving urgent measures for the modernisation of the Public Administration and for the implementation of the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan.
- Order HFP/1030/2021 of 29 September setting up the management system for the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan.

- Law 16/2021 of 14 December amending Law 12/2013 of 2 August on measures to improve the functioning of the food supply chain.
- ARELLANO PARDO, PABLO. "*El control de los fondos: La asignatura pendiente*". Tercera Jornada espacio registradores. 20 January 2022.
- BELTRÁN SÁNCHEZ, EMILIO. "La agricultura de grupo: las sociedades agrarias de transformación". Digital Library of the CEU-San Pablo University.
- CALLEJA CRESPO, DANIEL. "*Priorities and Challenges of the European Union*". Directorate General of the Legal Service of the European Commission. 18 March 2022.
- GRAJERA IBAÑEZ, GABRIEL. "El sistema grafico de los registradores: el guardián del medio ambiente." *El Economista*. 17 December 2019.